

0.5 (M3) to 1.0 mg/liter (M4) callus induction medium (see table).

Green plant regeneration ranged from 0 to 12.2% and was greatly dependent on genotype; Taipei 309 was the most responsive (Fig. 1c). Although the callus formation per anther could be increased

with increased 2,4-D concentration from 1.24 (M3) to 1.66 (M4) mg/liter, most calli on M4 were smaller and more difficult to regenerate than those on M3. M5 had low callusing (0.46 per anther) but high regeneration capacity of green and albino plants. The results indicate

that the high frequency of callus induction and green plant regeneration from isolated microspore culture could be obtained by using maltose as a carbon source and 2,4-D and NAA as hormones in the induction medium. ■

Restorers and maintainers for four cytoplasmic male sterile lines of rice

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We evaluated 84 hybrids, their pollen parents, and four isogenic maintainers (B lines) during Jul-Oct 1993 to identify maintainers and restorers for cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with two replications. Each genotype was planted in three rows with 10 plants each at a spacing of 20 × 20 cm. Fertilizer was applied at 120-60-60 kg NPK/ha and other recommended cultural practices were followed.

Pollen fertility was determined from florets in the upper part of the panicles before dehiscence. Pollen grains were stained with IKI. Cultivars with <5% pollen fertility were classified as potential maintainers, those with 6-20% as partial maintainers, 21-95% as partial restorers, and >96% as potential restorers (see table).

We are using the maintainers identified in this experiment in a backcross program to develop new CMS lines. The restorers are being used to develop new hybrid combinations. ■

Improvement in anther culture of japonica/indica crosses of rice

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We conducted a study to generate an anther culture-derived population for use in molecular mapping of genes for cold

Restorers and maintainers for four CMS lines. Coimbatore, India. 1993.

CMS line	Potential maintainers	Partial maintainers	Partial restorers	Potential restorers
IR58025 A	Akinishiki, Pada-shabag, J. Samba (VTS), 03866, 03891, 03898, C29, C32, C33, Dular	ASD16 Kundalika, Black Puttu, Co 41, Basmati 370, C12, C19, C36	Oozora, IR50, AS781/5, ADT2, ADT36, Co 29, C15, C24, C37, C39, C40, C41	IR62, IR70, IR72, IR74, W. Ponni, AS781/3, AS781/1, AS781/4, TNAU831520, 03860, 03862, 03877, 03880, 03881, 04001, C1, C2, C6, C7, C10, C13, C20, C22, C35, C40
IR62829 A	—	TNAU88013, Zhuhio, TNAU841434, TNAU802293	Thalisamba, TNAU831520, IR20, Co 41, Co 29, Co 43, ASD18	Ponni, Co 44, C18, TNAU92093
V20 A	—	—	ASD18, Co 41	IR64, IR62, IR70, W. Ponni
MS37 A	—	TNAU89093, J. Samba (VTS)	TKM 6, ARC6650, Bhavani	IR62, IR42, Ponni, IR20

tolerance. Anther culture efficiency was studied in two F₁ hybrids, M201/IR50 and M202/IR50, and their respective parents. M201 and M202 are cold-tolerant japonicas and IR50 is a susceptible indica.

Anthers were pretreated at 9 °C for 7 d and were cultured in the dark on N6 callus induction medium supplemented with 6 g agarose/liter, 2 mg 2,4-D/liter and 60 g sucrose/liter. Plant regeneration from calli receiving no treatment (treatment 1) was compared with that

from calli subcultured three times each at biweekly intervals followed by a preculture treatment with abscisic acid (ABA) at 5 mg/liter (treatment 2). Regeneration medium (N6 medium, 2 mg kinetin/liter, 1 mg IAA/liter, and 1 mg NAA/liter) was similar for both treatments.

Callus induction and regeneration, regardless of treatments, followed the order of japonica>indica>japonica/indica. M201 recorded greater callusing (35%) and regeneration efficiency (1.2% in

Table 1. Callus induction in parents and F₁ crosses.

Genotype	Anthers plated (no.)	Anthers producing calli (no.)	Callus production before subculture ^a (%)
M201	720	252	35.0
M202	720	244	33.9
IR50	720	169	23.4
M201/IR50 (F ₁)	10836	1150	10.8
M303/IR50 (F ₁)	11880	1224	10.4
Total	24876	3039	12.2

$$^a = \frac{\text{Anthers producing calli}}{\text{Total anthers plated}} \times 100.$$